

Short communication

FIRST REPORT OF BRACHODIDAE (LEPIDOPTERA) FOR SERBIA

ANA NAHIRNIĆ¹, ANDREW KING² and PREDRAG JAKŠIĆ³

1 National Museum of Natural History, Blvd. Tsar Osvoboditel 1, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria
E-mail: ananahirnic@nmnhs.com

2 Grovewood Close, 18, Chorleywood, WD3 5PU, United Kingdom

3 Čingrijina 14/25, Zvezdara, 11050 Beograd, Serbia

The family Brachodidae was established by Heppner (1979) as a replacement name for Atychiidae and placed in the superfamily Sesioidea (Heppner & Duckworth, 1981). In Europe only the genus *Brachodes* is known, with 14 recorded species (Kallies & Spatenka, 2002). However, Brachodidae are very poorly studied in Europe: as recently as 2002, four species were published as new to Europe by Kallies & Spatenka. To date, there has been no report of any species of the Brachodidae family from Serbia (Jakšić, 2016). We found *Brachodes pumila* (Ochsenheimer, 1808) on Mt. Stolovi in central Serbia. Consequently, this is the first report of *Brachodes pumila*, genus *Brachodes* and the family Brachodidae for Serbia.

Specimens were collected with an entomological net or by hand. The material is deposited in the collections of the authors and in the collection of Stoyan Beshkov in the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia, Bulgaria. A genitalia slide was prepared according to standard procedure (Robinson, 1976).

Collecting data: Serbia, Mt. Stolovi, Veliki Čukar, N 43°36'07", E 20°41' 11", 669 m, 11 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, 01.-02.07.2019, legs. A. King, A. Nahirnić & P. Jakšić (Figs. 1a, b, c). The bedrock is harzburgite. All specimens were found nectaring or resting on vegetation on the road verge where one of the dominant plants was *Centaurea calocephala* Willd. (syn. *C. atropurpurea* Waldst. & Kit.) (Asteraceae) on which the majority of the specimens were found nectaring. On 01.07.2019, specimens were found in the late afternoon and on 02.07.2019, from early morning until noon, when collecting ended.

Diagnosis: Sexual dimorphism is well expressed in this species. The males have characteristic antennae with tooth-like processes, with each segment somewhat bilobed (Kallies, 2001: 15, Fig. 14). What further distinguishes them from the similar *B. appendiculata* (Esper, 1783) and *B. tristis* (Staudinger, 1879) is the presence of a whitish costal spot on its forewing. Moreover, the shape of the white hindwing pattern is broad and continuous in *B. appendiculata* (Kallies, 2001). Fresh specimens of *B. tristis* have dense orange-yellow

scaling of the forewing that covers the narrow medial streak almost completely (Kallies & Spatenka, 2002). The female is recognizable by the shape of the white pattern on the forewing and the presence of white markings on the hindwing (Kallies, 2001). In the case of very worn specimens, genitalia can be used for identification. In males, the uncus has two apical tips and the aedeagus is thick and straight, with numerous cornuti (Kallies, 2001) (Fig. 2).

Habitats: *B. pumila* inhabits steppe-like grasslands in central and eastern Europe, and xero-montane grasslands in the southern part of its range (Kallies, 2001).

Global distribution: The species is known from Austria, Italy, Slovakia, Hungary, Croatia, Romania, Bulgaria, North Macedonia, Russia, Turkey, Syria, Kazakhstan, Kirgizstan, China (Kallies, 2001) and Ukraine (Geryak *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 1. *Brachodes pumila* (Ochsenheimer, 1808) at Veliki Čukar (Stolovi Mt.); **A** - female nectaring on *Scabiosa* sp. on 01.07.2019.; **B** - male nectaring on *Centaurea calocephala* Willd. on 02.07.2019. **C** - road verges with nectaring plants as habitat where *B. pumila* occurs at Veliki Čukar (Stolovi Mt.). Photos: A. Nahirić.

Acknowledgements: We are thankful to Jelica Novaković (University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology, Institute of Botany and Botanical Garden “Jevremovac”) for determination of *Centaurea* species.

References: Geryak, Yu., Dem'yanenko, S. & Konovalov, S. (2013). *Proceedings of the National Museum of Natural History*, 11: 5-27. [in Ukrainian, English summary]; Heppner, J. B. (1979). *Entomologische Berichte (Amsterdam)*, 39:127-128; Heppner, J. B. & Duckworth, W. D. (1981). *Smithsonian Contributions to Zoology*, 314: 1-144; Jakšić, P. (2016).

Ecologica Montenegrina, 7: 33-258. Kallies, A. (2001). *Nota lepidopterologica*, 24(1/2): 7-19; Kallies, A., Spatenka, K. (2002). *Nota lepidopterologica*, 25(2/3): 155-160; Robinson, G. S. (1976). *Entomologist's Gazette*, 27: 127-132.

Figure. 2. Male genitalia of *Brachodes pumila* (Ochsenheimer, 1808). Veliki Čukar (Stolovi Mt.) 02.07.2019. leg. P. Jakšić; slide number SR 3095.

ПРВИ ПОДАТАК О ФАМИЛИЈИ BRACHODIDAE (LEPIDOPTERA) У СРБИЈИ

АНА НАХИРНИЋ, ЕНДРУ КИНГ и ПРЕДРАГ ЈАКШИЋ

Извод

Фамилија Brachodidae је у Европи заступљена само са родом *Brachodes* који броји 14 врста. До сада нису постојали подаци о присуству представника ове фамилије у Србији. Ми смо пронашли *Brachodes pumila* (Ochsenheimer, 1808) на планини Столови у централној Србији. Ово је први налаз врсте *B. pumila*, рода *Brachodes* и фамилије Brachodidae за Србију.

Received: September 18th, 2019

Accepted: November 3rd, 2019